

ON THEORIES OF ADSORPTION INDICATORS.

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The cataphoretic velocities of silver halides with or without the dye indicators under the exact conditions of titrations have been measured. These observations are not in good agreement with the theory of adsorption indicators as propounded by Fajans or Kolthoff.

The applications of acidic and basic dyes as indicators to argentometric and other similar volumetric titrations have come into prominence mainly through the pioneering work of Fajans, Kolthoff and their collaborators.*

These titrations are based on the assumption that the indicators used change colour just when one or other of the constituent ions of the precipitate is in very slight excess.

When silver nitrate is gradually added to potassium iodide in presence of eosin as indicator, negatively charged colloidal silver iodide is formed in excess of iodide ions, and so cannot adsorb the negative eosinate ions. Thus the greenish fluorescence of the indicator ion persists till the end point is reached where the colloid usually coagulates. As soon as a slight excess of silver nitrate over that corresponding to the equivalent amount is added, the precipitate becomes positively charged and adsorbs negative eosinate ions and the colour of the precipitate changes suddenly and fluorescence disappears.

In reverse titration, the red colour, first formed, due to the adsorption of eosin ions by positively charged silver halide sol vanishes just when a slight excess of the halide is added and fluorescence again reappears due to the liberation of the secondarily adsorbed eosin ions by negatively charged chlorine ions (*cf.* Fajans).

Kolthoff (*Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 87) points out that the theory suggested above is not adequate, because the disappearance of fluorescence and the slight appearance of the colour of the precipitate takes place a little before the equivalent point is reached, where the precipitate is assumed to be negatively charged, and therefore electrical adsorption of the dye ions is not possible. Kolthoff suggests that the colour change arises out of the exchange by adsorption of the negatively charged halide ions of the surface with the fluorescent dye ions in solution.

There is, however, no experimental evidence regarding the manner of variation of the charge of these precipitates (either in the colloidal state or

* Fajans, "Radio-elements and Isotopes", 1931, p. 96 ; Fajans and Ardey Grüz., *Z. physikal. Chem.* 1931, 188A, 97 ; Kolthoff *et. al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 87.

when thrown down) under the conditions of titration to support assumptions made in the theories mentioned above. Fajans' theory was based on the observation of Lottermoser (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1905, **12**, 39; 1905, **13**, 374; Lottermoser and Roths, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, **62**, 359) on the variation of the charge of silver halides in excess of either silver or halide ions. It seemed desirable, therefore, to measure the charge of the silver halides under the actual conditions of titrations. The present paper furnishes only experimental facts.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The cataphoretic velocities of the silver halide particles either in the precipitated or in the colloidal state have been measured by the micro-cataphoretic method described before (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **13**, 370; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Sen-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1936, **13**, 421; Chaudhury and Sen-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1936, **13**, 670).

The velocities were observed at a single height (at 0.21 depth of the cell, where there is no endosmosis). It has been verified experimentally that the velocity observed at this height agrees well with that calculated from the observed velocities at half and one-sixth height.

TABLE I.

0.1N-KI (0.5 c.c.) and 0.1N-AgNO₃ (2 c.c.) used. Total volume = 100 c.c. containing 0.3 mg. of sodium eosinate.

Direct		Reversed		Mean		V × 10 ⁴ .
Time.	Current.	Time.	Current.	Time.	Current.	
13.6 sec.	0.38 m.amp.	12.0 sec.	0.352 m.amp.			
13.2	0.308	10.0	0.374	11.85 sec.	0.347 m. amp.	12.5
13.4	0.308	10.0	0.396			
13.1	0.33	9.5	0.396			
Sp. conductivity. = 2.711 × 10 ⁻⁴ mho.						
13.0	0.33	11.5	0.352			
13.2	0.33	11.2	0.352	11.96	0.348	12.41
12.8	0.33	10.8	0.374			
12.6	0.341	10.6	0.374			

Sp. conductivity. = 2.715 × 10⁻⁴ mho

Experiments were carried out with silver nitrate and potassium chloride, potassium bromide, and potassium iodide with eosin, fluorescein and methyl violet as indicators.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

I. Considerations of Experimental Results from the point of view of Fajans and Kolthoff when Lattice Ions of the Same sign as that of the Indicator Ions are in Excess.

The experimental results given in Table II are not in good agreement with either the theory of Fajans (*loc. cit.*) or that of Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

Total volume = 100 c.c.

Halide (0.1N).	0.1N-AgNO ₃ .	Dye.	Nature of charge.	$V \times 10^6$.
KI (4 c.c.)	3.85 c.c.	Without dye	-ve	35.1
	3.85	Eosinate (0.3 mg.)	-ve	35.04
	3.85	Fluoresceinate (0.3 mg.)	-ve	35.5
KBr (4 c.c.)	3.85	Without dye	-ve	34.04
	3.85	Fluoresceinate (0.5 mg.)	-ve	34.85
	3.85	Eosinate (0.3 mg.)	-ve	34.46
KCl (4 c.c.)	3.85	Without dye	-ve	31.2
	3.85	Fluoresceinate (0.3 mg.)	-ve	31.38
	3.85	Eosinate (0.3 mg.)	-ve	36.1

0.1N-Silver nitrate (3.85 c.c.) were added to 4 c.c. of a 0.1N-potassium halide (KCl, KBr and KI) with or without 0.3 mg. of sodium eosinate or fluorescein. With or without the indicator, the values of c. v. and hence the corresponding densities of charge of the colloidal Ag-halide are negative and the same in magnitude. According to Fajans, there should be no electrical adsorption of the dye ions under these conditions. These facts therefore appear to support the postulations of Fajans (*loc. cit.*). There are, however, exceptions. With eosin and silver chloride, an increase in c.v. is observed in presence of the dye ion. With the basic indicator used, it has been found that adsorption of the positive dye ion takes place even when silver ions are in excess, thus supporting the similar observations of Hodakow (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 127, 43; 1927, 129, 118) obtained analytically. Also at this stage of titration, there is absolutely no fluorescence* in the case of fluorescent indicators and a distinct reddish colour is to be

* The disappearance of fluorescence may be partly attributed to the quenching effect produced by the increasing concentrations of hydrogen ions and potassium nitrate formed as a result of the reaction.

observed in the precipitate. These facts are not in agreement with the theory of Fajans as already pointed out by Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*). In order to account for this change of colour, Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) assumed a sort of exchange adsorption between ions of the same sign on the surface and the dye ions in the solution. Thus according to Kolthoff there ought to be a change in the c. v. of the silver halides in presence of indicator solutions, for the reasons stated below.

(i) The dye ion is divalent* and a displacement of one halide ion by one dye anion (*cf.* as assumed by Kolthoff, *loc. cit.*) should have increased the negative charge. We find, however, that the c. v., *i.e.*, the density of charge, is not altered. In order to explain this constancy of charge from the point of view of Kolthoff one has to assume the displacement of exactly two chloride ions from the surface, which is rather unlikely.

(ii) Even if two halide ions are replaced by one indicator ion (which is, however, not probable), the surface character of the colloid complex and hence its power of adsorption, may change.

II. *Considerations of the Theory of Fajans and Kolthoff, when there is an Excess of Lattice Ions of Opposite Sign to that of the Indicator Ions.*

The c. v. of the colloidal halides, either in excess of silver or halide ions, with and without the dye, have been determined and are given in Tables III, IV, Va, Vb.

TABLE III.

Silver iodide.

0.1N-KI and 0.1N-AgNO₃ taken in a total volume of 100 c.c.

0.1N-KI.	0.1N-AgNO ₃ .	Without dye.		With 0.3 mg. of Na-eosinate		With 0.3 mg. of Na-fluoresceinate	
		Time after mixing.	$V \times 10^5$.	Time after mixing.	$V \times 10^5$.	Time after mixing.	$V \times 10^5$.
1.5 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	6.9 min.	22.3	6.9 min.	14.8	4.7 min.	13.65
		14.16	22.47	20.24	15.7	12.15	14.55
		22.25	22.75	30.32	15.46	21.25	15.6
				3 hrs.	charge -ve	3 hrs.	charge -ve
1.9	2.0	8.12	18.3	4.7 min.	-13.12	5.9 min.	-13.95
		19.21	20.3	12.15	-16.86	14.17	-23.1
		28.31	20.4	20.23	-15.93	23.27	-21.8
				31.35	-14.15		

* The p_H values of all the halide solutions and silver nitrate lie between 6 and 7 except that of KI which is a little alkaline. During precipitation, the p_H value is lowered in a number of cases but never comes down below 5 (*cf.* D. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 748). Under these conditions, the indicator anions are divalent.

TABLE IV_B*Silver iodide.*0.1N-KBr and 0.1N-AgNO₃ taken. Total volume = 100 c.c.

0.1N-KBr. 0.1N-AgNO ₃ .		Without dye.		With 0.3 mg. of Na-eosinate.		With 0.3 mg. of Na-fluoresceinate.	
		Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
1.7 c. c.	2.0 c.c.			5-8 min.	9.55		
				11-14	10.75		
				17-20	10.34		
				24-28	9.34		
				31-34	8.67		
				38-44	8.76		
				3 hrs.	-15.89		
1.9	2.0	8-11 min.	12.85	7-10 min.	8.71	5-9 min	-23.18
		18-22	17.33	13-15	9.14	17-21	-27.08
		28-32	16.17	20-24	7.18		
				27-30	5.93		
				3 hrs.	-19.37		

TABLE V(a).

*Silver iodide.*0.1N-KCl and 0.1N-AgNO₃ taken. Total volume = 100 c. c.

0.1N-KCl. 0.1N-AgNO ₃ .		Without dye.		With 0.3 mg. of Na-fluoresceinate.	
		Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
1.5 c.c.	2.0 c. c.	6-9 min.	21.43	8-12 min.	-5.55*
		14-18	25.17	3 hrs.	-13.57
					All -ve
1.9	2.0	5-9	9.09	6-10 min.	-8.2
		15-18	12.2		
2.0	1.0	5-9	-30.75		
2.0	1.5	6-10	-27.38		
2.0	1.9	6-9	-22.24		
		15-19	-21.3		

* Immediately after filling the cell, particles of both sign were visible moving slowly in these cases. The number of negatively charged particles appeared to be greater.

TABLE V(b).
Silver iodide.

0.1N-KCl and 0.1N-AgNO ₃ taken.		Total volume = 100 c.c.			
0.1N-KCl.	0.1N-AgNO ₃ .	With 0.3 mg. methyl violet.		Without dye.	
		Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
1.5 c. c.	2.0 c. c.	6-10 min.	31.4	6-9 min.	21.43
				14-18	25.17
1.9	2.0	5-9	19.83	5-9	9.09
		14-18	20.87	15-18	12.2
2.0	1.5	4-8	18.8	6-10	-27.38
		13-15	21.5		
2.0	1.9	5-9	10.74	6-9	-22.24
		15-18	12.64	15-19	-21.3

It would be found that in the majority of cases, increasing quantities of potassium halide was added to a constant quantity of silver nitrate (0.1N; 2 c. c. in 100 c. c.) with or without the indicator (0.3 mg.) keeping the concentration of silver nitrate in excess. As expected, the charge is always positive in absence of the dye. In presence of the indicators, the charge is also mostly positive. The value of the c. v. with dye is usually lower than that without the dye. The positive value of c. v. in presence of the dye diminishes with time and finally becomes negative in some cases. When, however, the amount of potassium iodide (0.1N) added is 1.9 c. c., the charge is negative from the very beginning, though without dye, the charge is positive. It appears that under these conditions, the type of electrical secondary adsorption and the subsequent deformation of the dye ions, as visualised by Fajans (*loc. cit.*), takes place. But the following facts which do not agree with Fajans' theory should also be kept in view

(i) The change of colour is instantaneous and does not vary with time whereas the charge varies with time.

(ii) This colour change is to be noticed from the very beginning of titration, that is to say when 2 to 3 c. c. of potassium iodide have been added to 2 c. c. of silver nitrate.

With 1.9 c. c. of KBr (Table IV), the charge is positive at the beginning in presence of sodium eosinate, but finally becomes negative. On the other hand with sodium fluoresceinate and KCl (*cf.* Table Va), the charge is always negative. Sometimes both the positively and negatively charged particles were visible immediately after mixing.

With methyl violet, a basic indicator with a positively charged dye cation (and KCl, Table Va), the charge has been found to be always positive irrespective of whether silver ions or chlorine ions are present in excess

(*cf.* the work of Hodakow, *loc. cit.*). Sometimes particles of both sign were visible just after mixing. These facts indicate the specific nature of the effects observed for particular pairs of adsorbents and indicators.

III. *Consideration of the Fajans-Kolthoff Theory when the Precipitate is formed from Equivalent Quantities.*

When equivalent quantities of silver nitrate and potassium halides are mixed, particles of both sign are persistently visible, when the dye is absent. In presence of the acidic dye ions the charge is found to be always negative (*cf.* Tables VI, VII, VIII) and the precipitate coloured.

TABLE VI.

KI and AgNO₃ in equivalent quantities. Total volume = 100 c.c.

0.1N-KI.		0.1N-AgNO ₃ .	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
2 c.c.	Without dye	2 c.c.	Both +ve and -ve.	3 hrs.	27.0
2	Without dye	2	After 3 hrs. all -ve.	3 hrs.	26.57
2	0.3 mg. Na salt of eosin	2	Both +ve and -ve.	5-9 min.	23.43
			-ve	15-18	26.65
2	0.3 mg. Na salt of eosin	2	-ve	5-9	22.06
2	0.3 mg. Na salt of fluorescein	2	-ve	18-20	25.12
			-ve	5-9	24.65
			-ve	16-20	31.9
1	0.3 mg. Na salt of fluorescein.	2	-ve	4-7	24.83
			-ve	15-19	30.15

TABLE VII.

KBr and AgNO₃ in equivalent quantities. Total volume = 100 c.c.

0.1N-KBr.	0.1N-AgNO ₃	Dye.	Nature of charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
2 c.c.	2 c.c.	...	Both +ve and -ve.	60 min.	16.35
2	2	...	After 1 hr. all -ve.	60	16.4
2	2	0.3 mg. Na-fluoresceinate.	Both +ve and -ve.	7-9	29.62
			-ve	15-19	32.45
2	2	0.3 mg. Na-fluoresceinate.	-ve	6-9	29.3
2	2	0.3 mg Na-eosinate	-ve	15-18	31.8
			-ve	7-10	17.5
			-ve	15-18	18.72
2	2	0.3 mg Na-eosinate	-ve	6-9	16.88
			-ve	15-19	18.6

TABLE VIII.

KCl and AgNO₃ in equivalent quantities. Total volume = 100 c.c.

0.1N-KCl.	0.1N-AgNO ₃ .	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁴ ,
2 c.c. Without dye	2 c.c.	Both +ve and -ve.		
		After 1 hr. all -ve.	1 hr.	22.66
2 Without dye	2	Both +ve and -ve.		
		After 1 hr. all -ve.	1	21.92
2 0.3 mg. Na salt of fluorescein.	2	-ve		8.6
			1	22.4
2 0.3 mg. Na salt of fluorescein	2	-ve		8.77
			1	15.65
2 0.3 mg. Na salt of eosin	2	-ve		28.56
			1	32.46
2 0.3 mg Na salt of eosin	2	-ve		24.5
			1	27.54

It is to be noted that the c.v. values of silver iodide and silver bromide are increased in presence of fluoresceinate ions, but do not change when eosinate ions are added (*cf.* Tables VI and VII). On the other hand, the c.v. values of silver chloride are increased in presence of eosinate but not in presence of fluoresceinate ions. Thus this clearly shows the specific nature of the adsorption of these ions. Moreover, we cannot assume the adsorption of either kind as the cause of the change of the colour of the precipitate, when the c.v. values are not altered (*cf.* discussion I; also *cf.* discussion II when the c.v. values are changed). Thus it is clear that the theories put forward either by Fajans (*loc. cit.*) or by Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) are not in general agreement with all the facts observed.

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